

Liquid Processable, Thermally Stable, Hydrophobic, Phenolic-Triazine Resins for Advanced Composite Applications

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Introduction and Objectives

- Combine a commercial PT oligomer with a liquid CE monomer to produce liquid processable systems
- Maintain thermal stability
- Improve processability
- Reduce moisture uptake

Results and Conclusions

The new blends provide:

- 1. Decreased reactivity** - $T_o > 188$ °C of PT-30
- 2. Better processability** - 2-fold reduction in viscosity via incorporation of 5 wt% of LECy
- 3. Better hydrolytic stability** - 0.36 % less moisture ingress after 126 days with incorporation of 20 wt% of LECy
- 4. Similar thermal degradation** - Y_c at 800 °C was 62.2 ± 2.3 °C (67.8 % for PT-30)
- 5. Similar longevity** - Mass loss after 64 days:
PT-30: 19.21 %, $1_{85}:2_{15}$: 26.49 %, and
 $1_{75}:2_{25}$: 30.92 %

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Thank you for your attention!

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